

No licensing agreements or messy definitions of a site

Blazing an even more revolutionary trail, the HighWire Marketing Group offers its journals on a "site-wide" basis governed by fair use. There are no licensing agreements or other legal complications. Upon registering your IP address or addresses, (something done by the subscriber's systems administrator,

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not HighWire.) online activation is simple and fast. Accredited users can even search HighWire off campus as long as their systems administrator has registered the IP address they are using. There is also no complicated definition of what comprises a site. The number of buildings isn't counted and their position in different parts of town isn't a factor either. In the spirit of keeping everything as simple as possible for the librarian and ensuring that scientific information reaches its users quickly and economically, HighWire's definition of a site is all buildings belonging to the subscriber within the city limits. Singapore for example, and Hong Kong, S.A.R., are both defined as one site. So if a subscriber has offices in Kowloon, the New Territories and Hong Kong island, they can all access HighWire at the single site price.

As for the future, the HighWire Marketing Group with database providers will be linking databases to full text HighWire journals. HighWire journals in other disciplines such as chemistry and engineering are also a distinct possibility. Watch this space...

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Information technology: What it means for science communication in developing countries

By Subbiah Arunachalam

In an interview she gave to a British newspaper immediately after she won the Nobel Prize for literature, the Princeton University professor Ms Toni Morrison said that it seemed as if writing about the life and sensibilities of Black People didn't really count. It was not thought important enough to merit attention. It was peripheral.

It is the same with doing science (or working in any other area of scholarly pursuit) in the developing countries. One's work goes unnoticed. One who works under adverse conditions in a developing country needs to achieve a lot more to win some recognition than those who work under much better conditions in the developed countries. Not surprising. After all, we live in an unequal world.

Harvard versus Hyderabad

Immediately following the Prague conference of biomedical editors in September 1997, *New Scientist* commented in an editorial¹ that when it came to choosing manuscripts for publication, editors of reputed international journals would more likely select the one from Harvard in preference to the one from Hyderabad, even though both manuscripts may be of comparable quality. Technology tends to exacerbate this inequality and further marginalize scientists on the periphery. The Internet, or for that matter any technology, does not come without its attendant problems. History has repeatedly shown that technology inevitably enhances existing inequalities. Take for example, scientific research in India. It is very important for researchers to get to know what is happening around the world as well as to let others know what they are doing.

Information is key to the growth of knowledge, and dissemination of information is crucial for scientific enterprise. In pre-Independent India, when scientists of the caliber of C.V. Raman, Meghnad Saha, J.C. Bose and S.N. Bose made their first-rate contributions to knowledge, the main vehicle for transmission of knowledge was the scholarly journal, and there were far fewer journals than now. Scientists around the world were almost at the same level as far as accessing information was concerned. True, most journals were published in Europe and Raman and his Indian colleagues received the journal issues a few months later than their European colleagues - the time it took for the boat to cross the seas.

Today there is a tremendous proliferation of journals and many of them, especially those published by commercial firms, are out of

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reach for libraries even in the West. The best academic science library in India at the Indian Institute of Science, receives only 1,562 serials, including those received gratis and on exchange. Thanks to the rising price of the dollar and pound sterling and the increase in the subscription prices of journals and databases, Indian libraries are cutting down on the number of journals and secondary services.

Can I call myself a scientist?

The situation in Africa is even worse. A Nigerian professor once told Seun Ogunseitan, the dynamic journalist turned information provider: "When you call some of us scientists, we laugh at ourselves. We know we can no longer make contributions to science. I do not know what my colleagues in Kenya or London have found, for example. So I cannot carry out an experiment and believe I am on the path to an original contribution to the sciences. If I have been giving generations of students the same notes for the last ten years, I should not call myself a scientist."² Ogunseitan continued, "Many people in our universities are not sure what is the state of science. Scientists often have to rely on what they are told, for example, by newspapers, by friends or by *Time* magazine. How can such people ever become authoritative and confident scientists?" In the United States and possibly Europe, many university libraries subscribe to upwards of 50,000 journal titles!

On top of this, many primary journals and secondary services have gone electronic. Current awareness services such as Current Contents Connect, abstracting services such as SciFinder of Chemical Abstracts Service and multidisciplinary citation indexes such as Web of Science are available on the web, at a fee that most university and research

laboratory libraries in developing countries cannot afford. Now even primary journals are accessible through password control on the web, such as those in the Science Direct service from Elsevier. Physicists have gone one step further; they circulate preprints through the Los Alamos e-Print archive long before they appear in print in refereed journals. This is a free service to physicists around the world.

No web access for most developing nation scientists

To access information in cyber space, one first needs access to the corresponding electronic technology. Often, technology diffuses rather slowly so that even today most scientists and scholars in the developing countries do not have access to the new information technologies. As a result, one's performance can be (and is) affected, not necessarily because one is a poor physicist or chemist but because one has poorer access to information through electronic means - be it CD-ROM, online or the web. As a recent editorial in *Science*³ pointed out, "Digital publishing has much to recommend it over print publishing for practical if not for aesthetic reasons. Uncomfortable tradeoffs are involved but the gains include ease of access, rapid delivery over great distances, and hypertext links from indexing services and bibliographic citations to the full text of cited documents." Hardly any laboratory in the developing world has web access to these databases. How can their scientists be equal partners in the worldwide enterprise of knowledge production? Thus the transition to electronic publishing from print will certainly widen the gap between the developed countries and the developing countries, and

will further marginalize the already marginalized scientists and scholars in the developing countries.

The Have-Nots and the Know-Nots

Most developing countries, especially those with large populations, do not have the necessary infrastructure (computer terminals, networks, communication channels, bandwidth, etc.) to compete as equal partners in the worldwide enterprise of knowledge production and dissemination. According to Bruce Girard, former director of Latin America's community radio Pulsar, 95 percent of all computers are in the developed nations; ten developed nations, accounting for only 20 percent of the world's population have three quarters of the world's telephone lines. Teledensity in India is about 1.5 lines per 100 persons. Till 1994, it was less than one per 100 persons. And most of the telephones are concentrated in the metropolitan cities. Many scientists do not have telephones on their desks. Those who have cannot make calls outside their towns, let alone overseas. Many universities do not have Email or Internet facilities. Some do have 1.2 or 2.4 kbps connections, but with such low bandwidths and poor terrestrial telephone connections, one can at best send and receive Email messages but cannot surf the net or do online searches on the Internet. The simple truth is the information superhighway is not bringing the fruits of cyberspace to all. Not yet. There are far too many people in the developing world who have not been touched by the information and communication revolutions - the have-nots and the know-nots who risk being always behind. True, those who have access to new technologies are much better placed than before. But the point is, a vast majority of scientists in developing countries do not have access to these technologies.

Take for instance the Los Alamos e-Print archive for physicists. Physicists at a few institutes in India - the Indian Institute of Science, Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Institute of Mathematical Sciences, and a few others - are using this facility. But physicists in leading universities like the University of Delhi, Banaras Hindu University and University of Madras do not have access to Internet or Email. Prof. Panchapakesan of the University of Delhi tells me that until he got a research grant from the Inter University Centre for Astronomy and Astrophysics, no one in the Department of Physics had direct access to the Las Alamos archive! In contrast, virtually every physicist in the United States and the UK will have access to the internet. The relative disadvantage of developing country scientists becomes obvious.

A number of journals, especially in the STM area, are receiving manuscripts by Email, getting them reviewed by Email, and so on. Some journals are available only in electronic form. Editors of such

international journals will naturally be reluctant to use referees from developing countries, even if they are exceptionally competent in their fields, simply because it may be extremely difficult to reach them electronically. Nor for that matter, will developing country scientists be able to publish their work in these electronic journals.

Concern from the United Nations

The United Nations is greatly concerned about the imbalance of access to communication facilities. The UN's Administrative Committee on Coordination issued a statement on Universal Access to Basic Communication and Information Services⁴ in April 1997 in which it comments: "We are profoundly concerned at the deepening maldistribution of access, resources and opportunities in the information and communication field. The information technology gap and related inequities between industrialized and developing nations are widening; a new type of poverty - information poverty - looms. Most developing countries, especially the Least Developed Countries (LDCs) are not sharing in the communication revolution, since they lack:

- affordable access to core information resources, cutting-edge technology and to sophisticated telecommunication systems and infrastructure;
- the capacity to build, operate, manage, and service the technologies involved;
- policies that promote equitable public participation in the information society as both producers and consumers of information and knowledge; and
- a work force trained to develop, maintain and provide the value-added products and services required by the information economy. We therefore commit the organizations of the United Nations system to assist developing countries in redressing the present alarming trends.

Electronic publishing may widen the knowledge gap

While the communication revolution is perceived as a liberating influence, what is most likely to happen is that in many developing countries (including India, I am afraid) scientists and scholars will be among the last to be reached by it. Therefore, the relative disadvantage they suffer (in the matter of access to information and knowledge) will only increase. The number of institutions and individual scholars having access to Email and Internet in developing countries and the rate at which this access has grown over time will support this contention. The speedy transition to electronic publishing will make it much easier for scientists and scholars in the developed countries to interact with colleagues and members of their invisible colleges. My major worry is that the low level of information and communication technologies in the developing countries would lead

to the progressive exclusion of a majority of their scientists and scholars from the collective international discourse that is essential for making progress in new knowledge production. Even now, when much publishing takes place in print, participation by India and other developing countries in high impact journals (such as *Science*, *Cell*, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*) is very low. The already existing gulf in the levels of science and technology performed in the developed and the poorer countries will be widened further, and that could lead to increased levels of brain drain and dependence on foreign aid of a different kind (knowledge imperialism).

What is needed to overcome the current crisis is a far more organized and systematic programme of action. Early introduction of satellite-based high bandwidth Internet access to tertiary educational institutions and research laboratories at low cost and differential pricing for information (journal subscriptions and access to databases) for developing countries are high on my agenda.

India can afford good internet connectivity but it hasn't happened

On both fronts, I am not happy with what is happening. For example, India can easily afford to invest in high-bandwidth Internet provision to the 100 or so cities and towns where most of the nation's research laboratories and universities are located. But this has not happened, although we go through the motions and give the impression of being serious. Within the last one year, there have been at least three initiatives. Prof. V.S. Arunachalam of Carnegie-Mellon University spent a few weeks in India, discussing with senior dignitaries (such as the then Finance Minister Mr. Chidambaram, and the technology-savvy Chief Minister of Andhra Pradesh Mr. Chandrababu Naidu) a proposal for networking the academic and research cities of India at a cost of a few tens of millions of dollars. He was even toying with the idea of getting the funds either as aid or as a soft loan from an international agency. The Scientific Advisory Committee to the Cabinet appointed a subcommittee with Prof. Roddam Narasimha as the Convenor to prepare a report on the subject. The report was submitted to the then Prime Minister Mr. I.K. Gujral. Now, a committee under the chairmanship of Mr. Jaswant Singh, Deputy Chairman of the Planning Commission, appointed by the Vajpayee government, has submitted its report. Let us hope the nation is lucky this time around.

But what is actually happening is disheartening. Different agencies in the telecom sector who have to implement and deliver, are quarrelling with one another. Indeed, this is characteristic of the Third World: it often takes far too much time for things to happen or to translate something from the realm of the possible to

reality. As for differential pricing, both publishers of primary journal and database producers are reluctant. In one rare exception, the Institute for Scientific Information, Philadelphia, offers its *Science Citation Index* at 50 percent discount to most developing country subscribers. Even then it is perceived as too costly!

I would not be surprised if very soon the gulf between the scientifically advanced nations and the others widen even further, leading to a further reduction of the role of developing countries in the enterprise of knowledge production, dissemination and utilization. Do I sound pessimistic? So did Toni Morrison.

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* Based on a talk delivered by the author at "Science Communication for the Next Millennium: Ninth International Conference of the International Federation of Science Editors," Sharm El-Sheikh, Egypt, 7-11 June 1998.

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